

Grain yield^a of variety Jaya as influenced by different methods of transplanting, Pantnagar, India, 1981.

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)
Row transplanting using 20- × 20-cm spacing on saturated soil surface	6.00
Random transplanting on saturated soil surface	5.62
Broadcast transplanting on saturated surface	5.96
Row transplanting using 20- × 20-cm spacing in about 5 cm water	5.90
Random transplanting in about 5 cm water	5.49
Broadcast transplanting in about 5 cm water	5.70
<i>F</i> test	ns
S.Em.±	0.23
C.V.(%)	7.0

^aAt 14% moisture.

Researchers compared seedling broadcast transplanting and standard row transplanting procedures. A randomized block design with four replications was used. The nursery was sown on 2 June 1981. Transplanting was 2 July.

Grain yields for the two methods were not significantly different (see table). Seedling broadcast was as effective as row transplanting. Broadcast transplanting took 60% of the time for regular transplanting. Rice was shallow transplanted, less root damage occurred, and plant population was increased at little extra cost.

Broadcasting has some limitations, however. Maintaining plant populations

is difficult when moderate to heavy rains occur after transplanting. Deep water (10 cm or more) makes the technique impossible.

Work is in progress to refine the technology and to define the economics in different situations. *h*

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Rice-based cropping systems

Management of fertilizer phosphorus in a rice-wheat rotation

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Two field experiments in 1977-80 measured the response of rice to fertilizer phosphorus (P) and evaluated direct, residual, and cumulative effects of recommended P (26 kg P/ha) in a rice-wheat rotation at Punjab Agricultural University Farm. The Fatehpur loamy sand soil is nonsaline (E. C. 0.12 mmho/cm) and alkaline (pH 8.5), and has low organic carbon (0.228%), available nitrogen (90 kg/ha), and available P (7 kg/ha), and medium available potassium (146 kg/ha).

Rice did not respond to graded levels of P (0, 9, 18 and 26 kg/ha) applied across treatments with 12 t farmyard manure/ha, 40 and 80 kg N/ha split applied, and 120 kg N/ha alone (Table 1). However, rice did respond to farmyard manure, nitrogen and the combinations.

In a second experiment in the same field, rice did not respond to direct applications of fertilizer P (Table 2). But wheat responded significantly and consistently. Yields with the application of

Table 1. Effect of phosphorus on yield of unhusked rice in Ludhiana, India.

Main treatment ^a		Yield (t/ha) at P levels of				Mean (t/ha)
FYM (t/ha)	N (kg/ha)	0	9 kg/ha	18 kg/ha	26 kg/ha	
0	0	3.02	—	—	—	—
12	0	3.66	—	—	—	—
12	40	5.22	5.13	5.35	5.09	5.20
12	80	6.75	6.98	6.90	7.02	6.91
0	120	6.96	6.84	6.85	6.78	6.86
Mean		6.31	6.32	6.37	6.30	6.32
LSD (0.05)						.60
P levels:	NS					

^a FYM = farmyard manure, N = nitrogen.

Table 2. Effect of differential application of recommended dose of P (26 kg P/ha) on grain yield of rice and wheat.^a

P treatment (kg/ha)		Yield (t/ha)		Total yield (rice +wheat)
Rice	Wheat	Rice	Wheat	
0	26	6.6	4.1	10.7
26	0	6.4	2.4	8.8
26	26	6.5	4.2	10.7
Control		3.1	1.2	4.3
LSD (0.05)		0.39	0.28	0.60

^aAv of 3 years (1977-78 to 1979-80).

26 kg P/ha to either or both crops in the rotation are similar. Direct, residual, and cumulative effects resulted from differential P fertilization.

Direct application of recommended P

to wheat achieved the highest yield. Wheat yield was 50% lower when P was applied only to rice in the rotation.

There was no cumulative effect from P application to both crops. *h*

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